

From Framework to Action

Reimagining Blended Teaching Through
EMBED+ and the Educathon

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embed⁺
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COURSE LEVEL

Teaching & learning
in the course

Proportioning & sequencing

Learning technologies & media

Blended interaction

Learner guidance

Learning workload

PROGRAMME LEVEL

Coherence across
courses

Curriculum coherence

Learning technologies & media

Learning workload

Learner guidance

Capacity development

ORGANISATION LEVEL

Enabling blended
education

Strategy & policy

Governance & finances

Support ecosystem

Capacity development

Technology ecosystem

Quality culture

THREE MATURITY FEATURES

1. DESIGN & DEVELOPMENT

Pedagogically grounded design that is aligned, implemented and iteratively improved.

2. INFORMATION-DRIVEN CHANGE

Systematic use of information to generate insights and inform decisions for improvement.

3. ADAPTIVITY

Intentional adjustment to learner diversity and context within ethical and legal boundaries.

FOUR MATURITY STAGES

1. AD HOC

Isolated

Uncoordinated and implicit practices.

2. DELIBERATE

Intentional

Designed with goals in mind; limited coordination and insight.

3. RESPONSIVE

Iterative

Evidence-informed adjustments to strengthen alignment and responsiveness.

4. EMBEDDED

Sustained

Integrated, coherent and continuously improved.

Transformation in blended teaching? Participatory and future-oriented professional learning

Integration of EMBED+
and TEFF Educathon

WHO PARTICIPATES?

Educators

Leaders

Support Staff

Students

THE HOST(S)

Each Educathon is hosted by 1-2 people.
Hosts

- are responsible for the overall facilitation of the Educathon (i.e. the PPT slides): Introduction, Input (if needed; see p. 8), Check-Points, activities/instructions, pitch presentation, wrap-up
- need to make themselves familiar with the whole Educathon before the event
- have the best overview over what's going on at any time
- keep reminding participants of time limits and rules
- are motivating & positive as well as confident that the Educathon will be a success! :)

FACILITATORS

Facilitators are needed to support both the host and the groups. They

- check in with the teams (without interfering in their learning process) to make sure every team is on the right path
- familiarize themselves with the material before the Educathon so they can explain it when needed
- observe and make sure nobody (accidentally) breaks any Educathon rules
- keep reminding participants of time limits
- eliminate any doubts on the learning journey and motivate the teams to "trust the process"
- inform the host if everything is going smoothly or if, for example, instructions need to be repeated or explained again
- join the host(s) in their confidence & motivation! :)

TEAMS (PARTICIPANTS)

In the Educathon, nobody learns all on their own. All work is (eventually) collaborative.
At the beginning of the Educathon, the group is split up into teams:

- Teams should not consist of more than 3-5 people to ensure that everyone has their time to shine and bring in their ideas.
- The number of teams - obviously - depends on the size of the learning group you're working with. Keep in mind that each team presents a pitch in the end: Should you have more than 8 teams (= 8 pitches), you'll need short breaks between the pitches for the audience to digest!
- When working with interdisciplinary groups or groups from different backgrounds, it is advised to have mixed groups.
- Also, randomly assigned groups hold great potential for more surprising results!

JURY (OPTIONAL)

If you decide to choose a winning pitch in the end (see p. 6), you may consider inviting a jury to decide. This certainly lets the Educathon end on a celebratory note!

Since the presentation of the 90-second pitches does not take a long time, the jury would only need to join the group to

- listen to the pitches
- decide on a winner (in secret; make sure the jury know they are supposed to choose the most innovative idea, not the most feasible!)
- announce their decision (+ a brief reason for their decision)

Therefore, you could consider asking colleagues, friends, experts, teachers, ... if they would be interested!

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